

MEDICAL SCIENCES

БИОХИМИЧЕСКАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ПАТОЛОГИИ ПОЛОСТИ РТА У ДЕТЕЙ И ПОДРОСТКОВ С ДЕТСКИМ ЦЕРЕБРАЛЬНЫМ ПАРАЛИЧОМ

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BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ORAL CAVITY PATHOLOGY IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS WITH CEREBRAL PALSY

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Актуальность. Доказано, что изучаемая популяция детей с детским церебральным параличом относится к группе очень высокого риска развития деформаций зубов и зубных рядов. Целью данного исследования было изучение механизмов формирования детского церебрального паралича с использованием комплексных клинико-лабораторных методов диагностики у детей и подростков с детским церебральным параличом. Материал и методы. Проведено комплексное клинико-морфометрическое исследование 299 детей и подростков, из них 143 пациента с детским церебральным параличом (основная группа) и 156 пациентов (контрольная группа) без соматической патологии. Оценивались стоматологический статус, качество жизни и биохимические показатели ротовой жидкости у обследованной популяции. Результаты. Установлено, что дети и подростки с детским церебральным параличом являются группой высокого риска развития стоматологической патологии, а распространенность, интенсивность и полиморфизм всех видов стоматологической патологии у них достоверно выше, чем у детей без коморбидной патологии (контрольная группа) ($p < 0,0001$). В основной группе отмечается больший удельный вес врожденной патологии челюстно-лицевой области по сравнению с контрольной группой, что формирует анатомические условия для развития детского церебрального паралича и является управляемым фактором риска ($p < 0,0001$). Заключение. Таким образом, окислительный стресс при нейропсихических заболеваниях наряду с генетически обусловленной дисфункцией иммунной системы включает в себя и социальные факторы, особенно детский церебральный паралич, а связь детского церебрального паралича и стоматологической патологии имеет трехсторонний отягощающий характер.

ABSTRACT

Relevance. It has been proven that the studied population of children with cerebral palsy is at a very high risk of developing deformation of teeth and dentition. This study aimed to investigate the mechanisms of cerebral palsy formation using complex clinical and laboratory diagnostic methods in children and adolescents with cerebral

palsy. Material and methods. A comprehensive clinical and morphometric study was carried out on 299 children and adolescents, 143 patients had cerebral palsy (main group) and 156 patients (control group) without somatic pathology. Dental status, quality of life, and biochemical parameters of the oral fluid in the examined population were assessed. Results. It has been established that children and adolescents with cerebral palsy are a high-risk population for the development of dental pathologies, and the distribution, intensity, and polymorphism of all types of dental pathologies are significantly higher than in children without comorbid pathology (control group) ($p < 0.0001$). The main group has a larger proportion of congenital pathology of the maxillofacial area compared to the control group, which forms the anatomical conditions for the development of cerebral palsy and is an uncontrollable risk factor ($p < 0.0001$). Conclusion. Thus, oxidative stress in neuropsychiatric diseases, along with genetically determined dysfunction of the immune system, also includes social factors, especially cerebral palsy, and the relationship between cerebral palsy and dental pathology has a three-way aggravating nature.

Ключевые слова: аномалии и деформации зубов, детский церебральный паралич, прикус.

Keywords: anomalies and deformation of teeth, cerebral palsy, occlusion.

Introduction

Quality of life is a multifaceted concept, conceptually represented by a subjective assessment of health status, including oral health, functional and emotional well-being, and satisfaction with care [5]. Measuring the quality of life in a child's dental pathology facilitates the assessment of dental pathology and the effectiveness of its treatment, which, however, in children with neuropsychiatric diseases, due to common intellectual deficits, can only be carried out through the "prism" of the perception of parents/guardians [1]. It is known that good health of the PD, which implies the absence of dental pathologies, is an important aspect of general health, especially significant for children with "other" capabilities [9]. Children with neuropsychiatric diseases have "special" needs for medical care, particularly dental care [4,11]. There is a sufficient amount of information about the clinical manifestations of major dental diseases in children with DSD, and the mechanisms of their occurrence and development are still formulated at the level of hypotheses and assumptions. It is believed with a high degree of probability that the reason for this is "damaging" factors that cause disturbances in the organogenesis and mineralization processes of teeth, operating at different stages of prenatal development. [5, 8, 12]. It is known that oral cavity is a complex environment consisting of many structures and types of tissues working in concert, and each of its structural units performs its unique function; for example, the only liquid structure in which all tissues and organs of the oral cavity are immersed in oral fluid, which is considered the most important component of the digestive process, as it serves for the initial breakdown of lipids and starches, owing to endogenous enzymes. Moreover, these components of saliva can be effective indicators of both local and systemic disorders [10]. Although proteomic and transcriptomic indicators have shown promising results to date, the information obtained about the GC microbiota and its immunological components remains one of the most intriguing aspects of the search for GC biomarkers. Although the mechanism by which these disease indicators appear in saliva has not been fully explained in all cases, these data indicate that GC may represent a significant source of discriminatory biomarkers for localized, systemic, and infectious diseases.

Modern views on the etiopathogenesis of neuropsychiatric diseases indicate the leading participation

of oxidative stress (antioxidant system) in the formation and development of this pathology, and the accumulation of free radicals is detected at all levels of the macroorganism, including PD [6, 16]. Several authors of their studies (studies) [2, 8] revealed obvious defects in the functioning of the (prooxidant and antioxidant systems) at the level of the oral cavity in children with POI, which can qualify as an antioxidant system in PO. However, the role of local factors, in particular, ionic and enzymatic balance, processes of lipid peroxidation, the activity of antiradical defense enzymes in the saliva of children with neuropsychiatric diseases, and the relationship between local changes in GC and the macro-level antioxidant system has been little studied [14]. The information content, non-invasiveness, and economic attractiveness of control group studies [11,13] contribute to the priority of this area in individual and screening examinations of GC homeostasis in this population. The pathogenic mechanisms of SP in children with neuropsychiatric diseases may be due to changes in the physicochemical properties of GC, such as a decrease in the volume of saliva production, acidic pH of GC, and disruption of the GC microbiota. One author studied the decrease in the level of antioxidants and buffer capacity in the gastric mucosa in children with neuropsychiatric diseases in comparison with healthy children; another argues that a decrease in antioxidant protection and lack of control of lipid peroxidation are recognized as the most important components of the pathogenesis of neuropsychiatric diseases, diabetes mellitus, diseases of the joints, gastrointestinal tract, and SP. The most important factor is the change in the antioxidant system in children due to the imperfect functioning of almost all organs and systems, and as a result, disturbances due to the influence of various external factors [6]. Considering all of the above, it is relevant to study the mechanisms of the formation of SP in cerebral palsy and the pathogenetic substantiation of new approaches in prevention, dental treatment, and subsequent lifelong medical and social rehabilitation of this population, including the development of innovative non-invasive diagnostic methods and an alternative standard for the provision of dental care for populations with cerebral palsy.

This study aimed to substantiate the mechanisms of SP formation using complex clinical and laboratory diagnostic methods in children and adolescents with cerebral palsy.

Material and methods.

A comprehensive clinical-dental and clinical-laboratory study was carried out on 299 children and adolescents, of which; by age groups was; 6-9 years (34.1%); 10-13 years (33.4%); and 14-18 year olds (32.4%), by gender - 168 (56.2%) boys; 131 (44.1%) girls; including - 143 (main group) sick children and adolescents; including - 44 (30.8%), (-28 boys; -16 girls) aged 6-9 years (MG -1); 39 (27.27%), (-25 boys; -14 girls) from 10-13 years old (MG -2) and 60 (41.9%), (-30 boys; -30 girls) aged 14-18 years (MG -3); study patients with cerebral palsy and mental retardation; 156 children and adolescents were selected as a control group; including - 58 (37.17%, CG-1), (-31 boys, -27 girls); 61 (39.1%, CG-2) (-33 boys, -28 girls) and 37 (23.7%, CG-3) (-21 boys, -16 girls) somatically healthy children and adolescents in need of stomatotherapy. Anamnesis, complaints, and a comprehensive examination of the maxillofacial area were collected; additional examination methods (obs-e) - index assessment - KPU, KPU + kp, ICDAS II, UIK, Plaque Index PLI, OHI-S by Green-Vermilion (1964), PMA (Parma, 1960), PBI (Muhleman, 1975), TER, Saliva-Check Mutans (GC) express test, studying the level of dental plaque cariogenicity, transillumination method for diagnosing carious defects and an X-ray (R) study was carried out - cone-beam computed tomography, orthopantomography, telerradiography and photo protocol. To study and analyze the medical and social aspects of the course and outcome in patients with and without CP, a questionnaire was used to assess the influence of dental status on the quality of life of children [3].

Biochemical studies of the regulation of the functioning of the immune system at the local level were carried out by determining the concentrations of anti- and pro-inflammatory cytokines (interleukin-1 (IL), IL-2, IL-4, IL-8, IL-10) (using a device from the Vector-Best company); immunoenzymes (Multiscan FC analyzer (Thermo Fisher Scientific)), obtained results PVC

- IL-1; IL-2, IL-8 and ProtBC - IL-4; IL-10 was expressed in arbitrary units (arb. units), and ng/l. Super-oxide dismutase activity was determined according to the method described by V.A. Kostyuka et al. (1990) and the data were presented as optical density, and the functional state of the prooxidant and antioxidant systems was calculated by the additional integral coefficient of oxidative modification of biomolecules, which was expressed in oxidative units of activity. Catalase activity was determined using the colorimetric method of M.A. Korolyuk et al. (1988) assessed the level of lipid peroxidation in GC by measuring the amount of two lipid peroxidation products that react with thiobarbituric acid. The test material was collected in the morning from an empty stomach.

The assessment of the state of mineral metabolism in the buffer capacity was studied based on the calcium (Ca) and phosphorus (P) content in the buffer capacity of patients; pH, viscosity, and buffer capacity were also studied. To establish the levels of total Ca and P in the gastric fluid, they were determined by the reaction with phosphomolybdic acid. The buffer capacity of the mixed saliva samples was determined according to the method of Leontyev V.K. (1974). The obtained data were processed using the parametric Student's t-test or non-parametric U-test using Excel MS Office 2013 software.

Results and discussion

The results obtained demonstrated the unsatisfactory state of the oral cavity and hygiene of the oral cavity ($p < 0.0001$) in patients with cerebral palsy compared to the control group. Quantitative assessment of dental plaque in the cervical region - Plaque Index PLI in the main group 3.0 ± 0.84 and the control group 1.64 ± 0.44 conventional units, revealed unsatisfactory oral cavity hygiene in patients with cerebral palsy. The number of erupted teeth was lower in the main group than in the control group (Table 1).

Table 1.
Index assessment of periodontal and the rate of unstimulated secretion of oral fluid condition in children and adolescents of both study groups (%).

Indicator	Clinical group (M ± σ)							
	Average by MG	MG-1	MG-2	MG-3	Average by CG	CG-1	CG-2	CG-3
OHI-S, standard unit	2,8±0,3*	2,6±0,5	3,0±0,1	2,8±0,5	1,4±0,40	1,5±0,22	1,02±0,01	1,3±0,33
OHI-S								
PMA, %	44,4±8,4*	41,3±5,1	48,4±8,3	45,2±3,4	32,4±5,42	28,2±5,8	26,0±6,2	39,5±6,08
PBI points	4,6±1,2*	3,4±1,9	5,0±1,4	4,02±1,	1,14±0,1	1,08±1	1,5±1,1	1,2±1
Caries prevalence %	98,9±2,04*	94,2±1,6	100±0,2	99,2±2,0	89,8±2,1	86,2±1,2	93,5±2	87,4±2,
Intensity caries CPE, u/e	8,8±0,1*	4,9±0,8	9,9±0,1	8,9±0,1	4,5±0,6	3,4±0,8	6,04±0,4	4,01±0,3

Note: CG - control group, MG - main group; * - $p < 0.05$ compared with the average values of the CG group; NSRS is unstimulated oral saliva.

In addition, the prevalence of caries in the primary teeth in the group was, on average, 98.9%, while among children in group 2, 100% of children had carious lesions in the permanent and primary teeth. In the control group, the incidence of caries was 89.85%, whereas in

the CG-2 group, the incidence was 93.54%. Furthermore, among the examined children and adolescents with oral health, the following were noted: hypoplasia in 31.46% of children, violation of dentition timing (47.55%), primary dentition (54.54%), anomalies in

the completeness of teeth (62.93%), endemic dental fluorosis (6.29%), abrasion of hard dental tissues (10.25%), dental injuries (30.76%), enamel necrosis (7.69%), enamel erosion (17.94% of patients and general patients in the control group only in -10.25%, -12.17%, -28.84%, -13.46%, -1.28%, -7.7%, and -1.3%, respectively.

In the main group, there were signs of inflammation of the periodontal tissue in 97.9% of cases; in the control group, it was -60.9%, while the pathologies of periodontal tissue in the main group were characterized by the presence of generalized forms of varying severity (94.4 %). The results of comparing the level of indicators of the OHI-S, PMA, and PBI indices confirmed the association of conditions for the development of periodontal tissue diseases in both groups. The level of unstimulated saliva gastric fluid in the main group of patients of all ages was up to 1.6 times lower than that in the control group. The results demonstrated the dependence of the OHI-S and PMA index on the level of production of unstimulated saliva RJ: the higher the unstimulated saliva RJ index, the lower the OHI-S and RMA index, and the better the hygienic state of the oral cavity. In our opinion, based on the results of the unstimulated saliva indicators, GC can qualify as a mild degree of xerostomia, and in patients in the main group, salivary dripping is aggravated by a decrease in the unstimulated saliva indicator of GC, which can disrupt the homeostasis of oral cavity in general and is the most important risk factor for the development of SP.

Moreover, it was established in children of the control group; malocclusion was on average, in CG-1 -16.0±1.3, CG-2 -21.1±1.7, CG-3 -16.1±1.4, MG-1 25.2±1.8, MG-2 -26.6±1.6, and MG-3 -38.5±2.67 out of the total number of subjects. At the same time, crowding of the upper jaws, medial bite, deep bite, and overbite increased across the age groups in the main group; the opposite was observed in the control group.

In the control group, dentition anomalies in the age group of 6-9 years of age are 8.6±4.5%; 10-13 years of age - 19.7±4.3%; 14-18 years of age is - 48.7±3.58%; in the group aged 6-9 years - 27.3±3.7%; 10-13 years of age - 30.5±4.08%; 14-18 years of age - 42.2±4.58%; At the same time, in the MG the number of malocclusions such as dental dystopia, infra occlusion and dental diastema increases.

Based on the results of assessing the quality of life of those examined in the group, parents, and the children themselves, they complained of aesthetic facial disorders (100%), including those associated with the location of the cut teeth and the appearance of the lips. The results of the assessment were as follows: physical discomfort and functional disorders, 3.0; emotional well-being, 1.2; social well-being, 2.0; family well-being 2.0 points; that is, emotional and social comfort were associated with aesthetic, speech, and limited free functional movements, while indicators of family well-being of children and adolescents were also rated unsatisfactory. Moreover, the more often parents are offended by problems with their children's teeth, the lower the quality of life of these children; the older the children, the less upset parents are about their children's dental problems.

When studying the concentration of Ca in GC with cerebral palsy, a decrease in Ca level was found relative to the indicators of the age-appropriate control group: in group 1 - 64.8±9.29; MG-2 - 75.3±10.92; MG-3 - 78.4±3.22; whereas in children from the control group, there was an increase in Ca indicators relative to the reference values. At the same time, differences in age range; 6-9 years; - 10-13 years, and 14-18 years between children in the control group and cerebral palsy group were not as pronounced, which was manifested in comparison with CG-1 and 2 and the average control group, by a less significant decrease in the Ca content in CG-3 compared with CG-3 (Table 2).

Table 2.

Indicators of mineral metabolism and physicochemical characteristics of GC in patients examined in different age groups.

Indicator	Clinical group (M ± σ)							
	Average by MG	MG-1	MG-2	MG-3	Average by CG	CG-1	CG-2	CG-3
NS RJ, ml/min	0,27±0,03*	0,24±0,04	0,22±0,08	0,33±0,02	0,40±0,07	0,36±0,1	0,40±0,04	0,43±0,09
Ca, mg/l	31,8±4,23*	35,9 ± 5,07*	31,1 ± 4,38*,#	28,5±3,05	72,8±6,32	64,8 ± 9,29	75,310,92^	78,4±3,22
P, mg/l	89,3±9,02*	108,2±12,01*	84,5±10,06*,#	75,2±8,04	151,8±15,82	140,5±16,82	152,1±17,7^	162,8±16,28
Ca/P, d.e.	0,48±0,5*	0,33 ± 0,06*	0,37 ± 0,07*	0,58±0,04	0,51±0,09	0,46 ± 0,09	0,50 ± 0,11	0,68±0,86
Viscosity, relative. Units	3,01±0,48*	2,28±0,268*	3,08±0,46*,#	3,68±0,46*,#	2,33±0,422	2,14±0,482	2,28±0,280	2,48±0,420
pH, units	6,34±0,44*	6,88±0,513*	6,28±0,445*,#	5,86±0,324*,#	6,55±0,344	7,01±0,389	6,44±0,458^	6,22±0,228^

Note: * – $p < 0.05$ in comparison with the indicator with the control group indicator according to the age range; ^ – $p < 0.05$ in comparison with the indicator of the CG-1 group; # – $p < 0.05$ in comparison with the indicator of group MG-1; d.e. – fractions of a unit; Ca – calcium; P – phosphorus.

Considering the changes in P indicators in the GC in the same groups, it is worth noting the statistically significant differences between the main and control groups, as well as between all age groups. It should be noted that in the GC group with cerebral palsy, the P content was sharply reduced compared to the control group (almost 2 times); - 89.3±9.02*; 151.8±15.82 resp. In addition, more significant pathological changes at the local level in the main group were confirmed by a progressive decrease in P content by 35.5% as they grew older, in contrast to the control group, in which an increase in P in saliva by 12.8% was observed with age, which was confirmed by the emergence of mixed saliva drooling [8], which in children with cerebral palsy aggravates the loss of biologically active gastric components involved in many physiologically important functions at the local level. Therefore, the deficiency of P-containing compounds resulting from this phenomenon may be accompanied not only by the expected drop in the remineralizing function of saliva but also by an imbalance of its entire ionic composition, including disruption of the buffer system, including dihydrogen and hydrogen phosphate ions, as well as difficulty in the synthesis of P-containing organic compounds in the oral cavity.

When studying changes in the Ca/P ratio in gastric fluid in the control group, it was partially revealed that there were no significant changes in this indicator in the CG-1 group compared to the CG-2 group. However, their change relative to the reference values was significant, which also reflected an increasing imbalance in the mineralizing function of saliva as the length of the pathological process increased. In addition, a significant difference in changes in the Ca/P ratio between the main group and control group was established, which was characterized by a significant increase in comparison with the reference values of the Ca/P ratio in groups CG-1 and CG-3, whereas in MG-1 and CG-2, no statistically significant changes were detected ($p = 0.146$). In

MG-3, there was a slight increase of almost 35% relative to what was expected for this age category.

When studying the acid-base state of mixed saliva, pathological changes in pH and buffer capacity were identified, which were characterized by a decrease in pH relative to the reference values in all treatment groups. A more significant decrease in pH was observed in children with neuropsychiatric diseases, in whom the decrease in pH was 12% in CG-3 and 14% in CG-2, compared to the reference values of the corresponding age ranges.

The latter, in all likelihood, may be associated not only with a longer duration of the disease in children of older age groups, but also with insufficiently high compliance in such patients. Even more significant changes were established when studying the buffer capacity, which was reduced relative to the reference values of the corresponding age groups to a greater extent in patients with cerebral palsy. This generally confirms the presence of a persistent disturbance of the acid-base state in the oral cavity with chronic damage to the nervous system [10].

When the functioning of AOD is impaired, an increase in the production of free radicals is observed; therefore, the content of reduced SH groups, products of oxidative modification (OM), and chemiluminescence indicators were assessed in the RG. Analysis of the data revealed a decrease in the content of reduced SH groups relative to the reference values of the corresponding age range in all groups. At the same time, the most significant decrease in this indicator was noted in the main group, which was significantly greater than in the control group.

This situation may be associated with the complete depletion of reduced SH groups in long-term pathological processes and reflects pronounced local dysadaptation and dysfunction of the low-molecular link of local AOD, which was confirmed by a significant increase in ACS modification products in the CC of patients from

the main group. A significant predominance of ACS processes and the vulnerability of RP biomolecules in the cerebral palsy group in comparison with the control group was revealed. In addition, in MG-2, the content of ACS modification products was 40% higher than in CG-1, which reflects the worsening of the antioxidant system as the duration of the disease increases in these children.

When studying the intensity of free radical oxidation (FRO) processes, it was found that the increase in

the intensity of the formation of free radicals and reactive molecules in all studied groups, including the maximum burst of chemiluminescence in comparison with the reference values of the corresponding age groups, was increased several times. In addition, the indicators of the maximum flash of chemiluminescence in the older age range, in contrast to the younger age range, were significantly higher in the main group than in the control group (Table 3).

Table 3.

The state of the low-molecular link, the activity of enzymes prooxidant system -antioxidant system balance, and the content of IL in the GC of patients in different age groups.

Indicator	Clinical group (M ± σ)							
	Average by MG	MG-1	MG-2	MG-3	Average by CG	CG-1	CG-2	CG-3
S-HL, conv. units	0,315±0,042*,#	0,234±0,047*	0,322±0,044*,#	0,389±0,044*,#	0,204±0,048^	0,171±0,044	0,198±0,022^	0,244±0,040^
Max VHL, conditional units	0,218±0,034*,#	0,122±0,056	0,245±0,061*,#	0,288±0,022*,#	0,101±0,028	0,084±0,014	0,110±0,042	0,111±0,014
SH-groups, wholesale units.	0,032±0,006*	0,040±0,008*	0,036±0,002*	0,022±0,008*	0,030±0,002^	0,040±0,006	0,030±0,008^	0,024±0,003^
POM, wholesale units.	0,232±0,022*,#	0,144±0,043*	0,228±0,042*,#	0,324±0,034*,#	0,123±0,045^	0,054±0,043	0,147±0,030^	0,168±0,060^
CAT, mmol min ⁻¹ l ⁻¹ / (1mg/protein)	40,2±4,38*,#	44,2±4,02*	39,8±4,78*,#	36,5± 4,78*,#	31,1±4,02	34,2±4,56	30,4±4,22	28,8±5,43
MPO, units Act.	2,70±0,44*,#	3,27±0,71*	2,69±0,25*,#	2,14±0,22*,#	6,00±0,44^	4,58±0,47	6,46±0,49^	6,98±0,49^
SOD, units l ⁻¹ / (1 mg protein)	35,5±3,68*,#	31,8±4,2*	35,8±3,44*,#	38,8±2,4*,#	17,9±1,98	19,8±1,40	17,6±1,94	16,2±2,11
IL-1, ng/l	45,7±4,4*,#	41,4±4,8*	44,8±5,6*,#	45,8±3,8*,#	34,06±4,4^	29,4±4,5	34,6±4,8^	38,2±4,6^
IL-2, ng/l	86,1±10,6*,#	65,1±8,3*	94,7±10,9*,#	98,4±12,9*,#	54,9±6,8^	41,8±5,6	58,2±6,4^	64,8±7,5^
IL-8, ng/l	121,7±13,4*,#	104,4± 12,4*	129,4±14,2*,#	131,2±14,8*,#	87,5±11,6^	81,8±10,4	88,4±11,4^	92,2±13,5^
IL-4, ng/l	18,5±2,8*,#	16,8±3,4*	18,8±2,6*,#	19,8±2,9*,#	10,6±2,4^	12,8±2,4	10,6±2,2^	8,4±2,1^
IL-10, ng/l	12,4±2,1*,#	9,8±1,8*	12,8±2,2*,#	14,6±2,4*,#	6,2±1,3	5,2±1,4	6,4±1,4	6,9±1,2

Note: * – p<0.05 in comparison with the control group indicator of the corresponding age range; ^ – p < 0.05 in comparison with the indicator of group 1; # – p < 0.05 in comparison with the MG-1 indicator; wholesale units – optical units; CAT – catalase; MPO – myeloperoxidase; SOD – superoxide dismutase; IL – interleukin.

In addition, it is necessary to note a more significant weakening of the long-term mechanisms of ARS in the main group compared to the control group between the age groups in MG-1 and MG-2, which was 48-50% higher than that in CG-1 and CG-2. Analysis of the integral index (IIC), which reflects the functioning of the low-molecular link pro-oxidant system-antioxidant system, was found to be significantly increased in patients of all groups. Among other things, it was found that older patients often had more severe disorders than younger patients. At the same time, in those examined from the control group, multidirectional changes were sometimes observed in comparison to the indicators of the control group. In turn, a decrease in

myeloperoxidase activity in the control group indicates decompensation in the first line of antimicrobial defense, which is especially obvious when comparing these indicators with the average values in the control group. At the same time, the level of myeloperoxidase activity was lower in the GC in MG-1 and 2 compared than in CG-1, and in MG-3, these differences reached an even greater magnitude, which reflects a more pronounced decompensation of local homeostasis in children from MG-3.

A study of superoxide dismutase activity revealed an increase relative to the corresponding age reference values in all groups of patients examined. The greatest

differences within the same age range were noted between the MG-2 and CG-2 groups. The data obtained indicate excessive local production of superoxide anion radicals, which may be associated with the activation of the cellular membrane-bound multimolecular enzyme complex (NADPH oxidase) of phagocytic cells in the PR, with increased microbial invasion and uncontrolled SRO reactions as a result of impaired permeability of the blood-salivary barrier against the background of decompensation of the systemic pathological process in children with cerebral palsy. A distinctive feature of the functioning of the AOD enzyme unit under physiological conditions is the interaction between the main enzymes: dismutating superoxide anion radicals and destroying hydrogen peroxide without the formation of toxic products. This relationship is explained by the ability of the products of these chemical reactions to act as allosteric regulators for the mentioned enzymes.

In connection with the above, it was decided to consider the possibility of an integral determination of disturbances in the intensity of FRO, taking into account the assessment of the contribution of the imbalance of enzymatic antioxidant processes to the formation of disturbances in oxidative metabolism at the local level. For this purpose, the integral indicator of the functioning of ARZ GC enzymes was also calculated and was significantly reduced in children with neuropsychiatric diseases relative to the reference values ($p < 0.05$). The absence of statistically significant differences in the integral indicator of the functioning of ARZ enzymes in the control group patients, relative to the age-specific reference values, indicates the implementation of adaptation mechanisms in the majority of those examined in these groups, aimed at accelerating the utilization of excess hydrogen peroxide during the formation of stoma, for example, due to active microbial invasion.

When studying the characteristics of IL-1 production in the oral cavity of the observed patients, its increase was observed in all groups, but was somewhat greater in the presence of MG, taking into account the fact that IL-1 is the initiator of the launch of the cytokine cascade in the oral mucosa, while enhancing not only its synthesis but also the production of IL-6, IL-8, and tumor necrosis factor, and its increase in the GC relative to the reference values, according to age. The latter is especially unfavorable when there is a decrease in the local level of IL-4 and can lead to chronicity of the inflammatory process with a long-term increase in IL-1 synthesis. The increase in IL-1 production in age groups was higher in the main group was greater than that in the control group. IL-2 was also observed to increase in concentration in the GC relative to the reference values in all treatment groups, to a greater extent in the main group. Moreover, IL-8, which plays an important role in the development and progression of the inflammatory process in stomatitis, was significantly increased in GC relative to the reference values in all groups of patients. Elevated levels of IL-8 are highly correlated with granulocyte infiltration of the oral mucosa. Simultaneously, in the focus of inflammation, the formation of IL-8 begins following the entry of IL-1

and tumor necrosis factor, leading to the formation of autoimmune processes.

The change in the concentration of IL-10 was similar to that of IL-4 and was characterized by higher values in the main group, the values of which exceeded the reference values for the corresponding age range. IL-10, a lymphokine produced by T-helper-2 cells, can be considered an antagonist of several cytokines, reducing the release of IL-1b, tumor necrosis factor, and IL-6 by activated monocytes. In addition, additive and synergistic interactions have been identified between IL-10 and IL-4 in the process of regulating the strength and duration of immune response. The essential role in the implementation of the immune response of the previously discussed cytokines (IL-1, IL-2, IL-4, IL-8, and IL-10) is determined by their ability to coordinate both innate and adaptive immunity. When IL-1, together with antigen degradation products, is exposed to T-helper cells, the release of IL-2 is observed, which is an activator of the growth of not only T lymphocytes but also NK cells, which is accompanied by the release of various types of humoral factors in the gastric mucosa. It is necessary to point out that the increase in the production of both ProtBC and PVC in the GC of older children was significantly higher. Thus, objective identification of the dental needs of children and adolescents with cerebral palsy made it possible to identify a connection between SP and psychoneurological pathology, expressed in a significantly higher prevalence, severity, and polymorphism of dental diseases in the main group than in the control group: distribution and frequency of occurrence of dental caries and non-carious lesions of teeth, hypoplasia, violation of the timing of dentition, primary dentition, anomalies in the completeness of teeth, endemic dental fluorosis, abrasion and trauma of teeth, necrosis, and erosion of enamel; signs of inflammation of the periodontal tissue and pathology of the oral mucosa are noticeably higher in patients in the main group than in the control group. It has also been established that the average number of malocclusions in CG-1 was 16.0 ± 1.3 , CG-2 -21.1 ± 1.7 , CG-3 -16.1 ± 1.4 , MG-1 25.2 ± 1.8 , MG-2 -26.6 ± 1.6 , and MG-3 -38.5 ± 2.67 out of the total number of subjects; at the same time, crowding in the upper jaw, medial bite, deep bite, and open bite increased across age groups in the main group; these results in the control group became the opposite. The results obtained for stomas in children and adolescents with cerebral palsy are intense and vary and affect all nosological forms of stoma, including congenital; however, the results we obtained on the distribution of some stomas do not coincide with the opinions of several studies [7, 15].

In addition, as a result of the study, it was established that in the GC group with cerebral palsy, the P content was sharply reduced compared to the control group (almost two times); a significant difference in changes in the Ca/P ratio between the main group and control group, which was characterized by a significant increase in comparison with the reference values of the Ca/P ratio in groups CG-1 and CG-3, while in MG-1 and MG-2 there were no statistically significant changes detected ($p=0.146$); an increase in the intensity of the formation of free radicals and reactive molecules

in all examined exhaust gases; an integral indicator reflecting the functioning of the low-molecular link of POS ProtOS, a significant increase was established in patients of all treatment groups, and it was noted that the increase in the production of both PVC and ProtBC in the GC of children of the older age range was significantly higher.

Conclusion

It was also established that the presence of more pronounced disturbances in the functioning of the system regulating the homeostasis of oral cavity in the control group contingent, while significant relationships were established between pathological changes in the enzymatic and low-molecular units of the antioxidant system and disorders of mineral metabolism, expressed to a greater extent than in the control group, in the results allow us to assert that oxidative stress in PD, along with genetically determined dysfunction of the immune system, especially in children of the older age group, is one of the leading links in the pathogenesis of cerebral palsy in cerebral palsy, and the relationship between cerebral palsy and cerebral palsy is of a bilaterally aggravating nature. The results of clinical, biochemical, and sociological research allow us to classify cerebral palsy as a general risk factor for the development of stomatology, which is the basis for reframing the procedure for providing stomatology to the specified contingent.

References

1. Belikova A.A. Features of the management of dental patients with persistent disorders of the central nervous system, Bulletin of Medical Internet Conferences, 2015, 5 (10), 166. (in Russ.).
2. Volobuev V.V. Optimization of dental care for children with psychoneurological disorders, PhD abstract, 2017, 24, 122. (in Russ.).
3. Gafforov S.A., Mitronin A.V., Belenova I.A., and Yarieva O.A. The importance of medical and social factors in the etiology of carious and non-carious diseases among children and adolescents, Journal "Cathedra", 2019, 69, 62-66. (in Russ.). <https://zenodo.org/badge/DOI/10.5281/zenodo.7045681.svg>
4. Gulenko O.V. "Strategy for comprehensive dental care for children with psychoneurological diseases." Dis. DSc, Krasnodar. 2019. (in Russ.).
5. Kononova A.E. Socio-economic factors of child health in Russia, Sociological Research, 2016, 4, 94-102. (in Russ.).
6. Ozornin A.S., Ozornina N.V., Govorin N.V. Changes in the processes of lipid peroxidation and the content of fatty acids in erythrocyte membranes in patients with paranoid schizophrenia, Russian Psychiatric Journal, 2017, 2, 47-53. (in Russ.).
7. Pronina L.A. Epidemiology of mental disorders in children, Minsk: Belarusian 2015, 06/28/2015. (in Russ.).
8. Khagurova S.B. Features of mineral metabolism, antibacterial and antioxidant protection in the oral cavity during dental caries in children with neuropsychiatric disorders, diss. PhD., Krasnodar, 2018, 24. (in Russ.).
9. Avraamova O.G., Pakhomova Y.V. Oral health status in children with intellectual disability living in organized groups, Stomatologiya, 2016, 95, 52-55. (in Russ.).
10. Diéguez-Pérez M., de Nova-García M-J., Mourelle-Martínez M.R., Bartolomé-Villar B. Oral health in children with physical (Cerebral Palsy) and intellectual (Down Syndrome) disabilities: Systematic review, Journal of Clinical and Experimental Dentistry, 2016, 8(3), 337-343.
11. Gaffarov S.A., Khamroev F.Sh., Madaminova N.S., Shamsieva M.O. (2023), Anthropometric and clinical-dental condition of the maxillary system and oral organs in patients with cerebral palsy, Znanstvena misel journal, Slovenia, ISSN 3124-1123, 75, 32-37.
12. Filipp M. E., Travis B. J., Henry S. S., Idzikowski E. C., Magnuson S. A., Megan Y. F., Hellenbrand D. J., Hanna A. S., Hellenbrand D. J. (2019), Differences in neuroplasticity after spinal cord injury in varying animal models and humans, Neural Regeneration Research, 14(1), 7-19, January. DOI: 10.4103/1673-5374.243694
13. Palaska P.K., Antonarakis G.S. (2016), Prevalence and patterns of permanent tooth agenesis in individuals with Down syndrome: a meta-analysis, European Journal of Oral Sciences, 124 (4), 317-328.
14. Sixou J.L., Vernusset N., Daigneau A., Watine D., Marin L. (2017), Orofacial therapy in infants with Down syndrome, Dentofacial Anom Orthod, 20, 108.
15. Tóthová L., Celec P. (2017), Oxidative Stress and antioxidants in the diagnosis and therapy of periodontitis, Front Physio, 8, 1055.
16. Wong H.M., McGrath C. (2019), Effectiveness of a visual-verbal integration model in training parents and their preschool children with intellectual and developmental disabilities to dispense a pea-sized amount of fluoridated toothpaste, Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities, 32(3), 657-665.
17. Salivary transcriptomic biomarkers for detection of resectable pancreatic cancer, Gastroenterology, 138, 949-957.